

ELIXIR Commissioned Service report for deliverables/milestones

Document info

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Version	Revised by	Date	Comment
0.1	Evangelos (Vangelis) Pafilis, HCMR, Greece	24.06.2025	Draft version
1.0.0	Evangelos (Vangelis) Pafilis, HCMR, Greece	27.06.2025	Final draft version
1.0.1	Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou, DUTH, Greece Helle Tessand Baalsrud, NMBU, Norway	27.06.202	Submitted version
1.0.1	Project Co-Leads: Name, Last name 1 Name, Last name 2		

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation

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Executive Summary

The "Odyssey" project is developing a web portal designed as an intuitive interface for researchers, educators, and citizens to explore molecular biodiversity (through case studies from Greece and Norway).

The portal aims to provide up-to-date, interactive, georeferenced molecular biodiversity information, enhancing accessibility and utility.

Key data sources include the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). ENA offers a range of sequence data from barcodes to full genomes, some of which include geographical details. GBIF provides biodiversity occurrence data, partially georeferenced.

Odyssey plans to aggregate data from such data sources, overlaying them on maps and organizing them by taxonomic groups and regions.

Six months into the project, this milestone is a technical summary detailing queries posed to ENA and GBIF, including technical information on how these queries function to retrieve specific data fields and their customization for Greek and Norwegian biodiversity contexts. This report also proposes methods for enhancing data quality and metadata, as well as more fine-grained queries to enrich Odyssey's content.

Outcomes and Impacts

Data Retrieval Queries

The following tables display the queries submitted to ENA and GBIF, along with comprehensive background details for each dataset.

Background Information	
European Nucleotide Archive resource	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena
General Guide on ENA Data Retrieval	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/retrieval/general-guide.html
How to Access ENA Programmatically documentation	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/retrieval/programmatic-access.html
ENA Portal API v2 Programmatic access to data held within ENA (EMBL-EBI, May 2023)	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CwoY84MuZ3SdKYocqssumghBF88PWxUZ/edit
ENA Portal API Base URL	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/

Queries	
Basic Query for Greece-related sequences	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search?result=sequence&query=country=%22Greece%22&fields=accession,country,first_public,altitude,location,isolation_source,host,host_tax_id,tax_division,tax_id,scientific_name,tag,keywords,topology
Basic Query for Norway-related sequences	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search?result=sequence&query=country=%22Norway%22&fields=accession,country,first_public,altitude,location,isolation_source,host,host_tax_id,tax_division,tax_id,scientific_name,tag,keywords,topology
Limitations - Considerations	
A 50 requests per second upper limit applies (if breached, a "Too Many Requests" (HTTP status code 429) is returned)	

Table 1: ENA - the European Nucleotide Archive: background information, links to API documentation. Note that the API calls list the sequence metadata to be retrieved

Background Information	
Global Biodiversity Information Facility	https://www.gbif.org/
GBIF API Documentation	https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/openapi/
GBIF API Overall Description	<i>"The GBIF API provides a programmatic way to query and publish data on GBIF.org. It can be useful or necessary to use the API to make advanced queries, not supported by the website, include the results of GBIF queries in scripts, workflows or analyses, which can then be repeated reliably and automatically, embed GBIF data into other websites. The GBIF API is RESTful and most queries return data in JSON format. The API should be considered stable, as should this accompanying documentation."</i>

	(source: GBIF API documentation, "BIF API Reference" section)
GBIF API Base URL	https://api.gbif.org/
Queries	
Example Query for Greece-related occurrences	https://api.gbif.org/v1/occurrence/search/?country=GR&limit=300&offset=1200
Example Query for Norway-related occurrences	https://api.gbif.org/v1/occurrence/search/?country=NO&limit=300&offset=1200
Limitations - Considerations	
<p><i>"If you are integrating the GBIF API into a website or app, we recommend you set the HTTP User-Agent to a URL or email address. We can then contact you if there is a problem."</i></p> <p><i>"Frequent queries to some search APIs may be rate limited, depending on our server load. If this happens, you will receive an HTTP 429 error, and you should reduce your query rate and try again."</i></p> <p>(source: GBIF API documentation, "Rate Limits" section)</p>	

Table 2: GBIF - The Global Biodiversity Information Facility: background information, links to API documentation. Please note the limit and offset algorithmic mechanism to retrieve large datasets iteratively

Integration with the Odyssey Web Application

Greece-related sequence information (retrieved from ENA) has been ingested by the Odyssey working prototype (Figure 1). It serves, thus, as a development and testing dataset.

ENA retrieved data for Norway is currently under development¹. Additionally, GBIF retrieved occurrence datasets for both Greece and Norway, which are to be wrapped and ingested in the coming development cycles.

¹Related Odyssey Github pull request: <https://github.com/BiodataAnalysisGroup/ELIXIR-BFSP-Odyssey/pull/27>

Figure 1: Greece-related sequence information (retrieved from ENA) (with geographical coordinate information) shown in an interactive map

Integration into Galaxy

Part of the work has been focused on integration with Galaxy. To this end, a wrapper for Odyssey has been developed², enabling it to be used as a Shiny app service within Galaxy workflows.

Further Data Query Exploration

INSDC Sequences in GBIF

The ongoing collaboration between ENA and GBIF³ can offer access to "three different datasets containing sequence-based records, records associated with host organisms, and records associated with environment sample identifiers"^a (Figure 2). Such datasets have been noted for both data retrieval and possible user-Odyssey application interaction, such as selecting which dataset entries to view on the map.

²Related Odyssey Github pull request: <https://github.com/BiodataAnalysisGroup/ELIXIR-BFSP-Odyssey/pull/26>

³ 14 September 2021, Cross-infrastructure collaboration with ENA improves processing, quality of DNA-derived occurrences, <https://www.gbif.org/news/3jpFT9gvsj9zwcupx1gOKU/cross-infrastructure-collaboration-with-ena-improves-processing-quality-of-dna-derived-occurrences>

Figure 2: INSDC datasets returned the GBIF dataset tool⁴

GBIF-Improved Occurrence Information

GBIF has already flagged and corrected cases of erroneous geographical coordinates, such as reverse longitude and latitude.

Such an “issue” clause in the JSON record of GBIF occurrences (**Figure 3**) has been noted and is to be considered upon organizing and presenting Greece and Norway’s data.

⁴ INSDC datasets returned the GBIF dataset tool, source: <https://www.gbif.org/search?q=insdc>

```

← → ↻ 🌐 api.gbif.org/v1/occurrence/3350869948
Pretty print 
{
  "issues": [
    "GEODETTIC_DATUM_ASSUMED_WGS84",
    "CONTINENT_DERIVED_FROM_COORDINATES",
    "PRESUMED_SWAPPED_COORDINATE",
    "TAXON_MATCH_TAXON_CONCEPT_ID_IGNORED",
    "TAXON_MATCH_TAXON_ID_IGNORED"
  ],
  "lastInterpreted": "2025-05-24T12:28:51.803+00:00",
  "references": "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/KT870115",
  "license": "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode",
  "isSequenced": true,
  "associatedSequences": "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/api/embl/KT870115",
  "identifiers": [
    {
      "identifier": "KT870115"
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 3: part of the GBIF 3350869948 occurrence data⁵. Please note the “issues” PRESUMED_SWAPPED_COORDINATE flag

Next Actions

Summarizing the above, the next Odyssey actions, in terms of data retrieval (i.e., Activity 1) and software development (i.e., Activity 2), can be classified into:

Short-term Actions

In preparation for the “M5.2 (Activity 2) First demo of the Odyssey framework NO-NMBU” coming up on M24 (i.e., December 2025), an Odyssey instance should be prepared. This will enable users to view the molecular biodiversity data of the following two combinations:

- A. of Greece, Norway, or both
- B. from ENA, GBIF, or both (based on the **Table 1** and **Table 2** queries)

Mid-/long-term Actions

Beyond the M5.2 Milestone, follow-up implementations could support:

- A. the browsing of the additional GBIF datasets (see **Further Data Query Exploration** section)
- B. the rendering of the Odyssey R shiny application accessible via Galaxy

⁵ Part of the GBIF 3350869948 occurrence data in JSON format: <https://api.gbif.org/v1/occurrence/3350869948>